

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable 3.3

Report on the establishment of the interactions with SF and IB

Workpackage 3

Partnership
FOR THE
Assessment
OF
Risks
FROM
Chemicals

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Abstract

The report describes the scope, process, selection criteria and, finally, composition of the PARC Stakeholder Forum (SF) and International Board (IB). It includes the different steps followed to populate the SF and IB of the partnership including the internal consultation procedure involving the different management instances of PARC, namely the Management Board (MB), the Grant Signatory Board (GSB) and the Governing Board. The report outlines the algorithmic tool that was developed and used to screen candidates for both the SF and the IB allowing us to integrate different criteria and produce an overall assessment through its implementation. This assessment was further discussed within PARC MB and the final decision was taken at the level of the PARC GSB.

Keywords

Stakeholder Forum, stakeholders, International Board, experts, representatives, chemical risk assessment, external communication, science-to policy (S2P) interaction, scientific input.

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1. Introduction

1.1 The role of the Stakeholder Forum (SF)

The PARC Stakeholder Forum (SF), as described in the PARC grant agreement will hold a maximum of 15 members and accompanies PARC for the duration of 7 years. The SF shall facilitate interaction, i.e. regular communication, targeted information and continuous exchange on PARC's process and current developments in chemical risk assessment (RA) of human health and the environment with relevant European stakeholders.

It shall (i) foster collaboration and synergies with stakeholders from Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), academia, industry/business associations, employer and worker representative bodies and consumer organisations, (ii) provide regular information on current developments or concerns in relation to chemical RA of human health and the environment to the Management Board (MB), Governing Board (GB) and Grant Signatory Board (GSB) of PARC, (iii) provide feedback and input on performance indicators, priorities and key elements of PARC, (iv) boost the impact of PARC through dissemination of knowledge and interaction with stakeholders to enhance the uptake of results and communication to different audiences, (v) co-create a living and sustainable Partnership, seeking both to promote and to benefit from mutual interests, needs and priorities as well as strategic and technical aspects to ensure the progress of chemical RA and thereby enhance the accountability and credibility of the activities and results of the Partnership.

1.2 The role of the International Board (IB)

The International Board (IB) consists of 15 high-level experts in the field of chemical RA who will provide expertise in the different scientific and policy topics tackled by the Partnership. Experts come from international chemical RA platforms, international organisations, scientific advisory boards, scientific committees of the EU Agencies, scientific associations with well recognised expertise, top-level academia, etc. Members of the IB will bring their knowledge on the state of the art in chemical RA, on relevant key initiatives, innovations, and key players in chemical RA, globally. Further experts in the field of policy development and effective scientific support to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (CSS), are included as well. Finally, people able to provide input on novel policy approaches or policies that have been proven successful outside the EU are also included in the Board.

The IB will provide knowledge from within and outside the European Union and will inform on recent developments on a global level; thus, it will promote a critical reflection on the partnerships' activities and results, increasing their quality and enhancing synergies and innovation. Its members have been selected in such a way as to bring in complementary information from various parts of the world, topics of research and legislative domains and jurisdictions. Meetings of the IB will be organised annually to obtain knowledge from outside PARC, to provide information on recent developments and to enhance synergies and innovation. The IB may also be called upon to review key projects of PARC prior to their launch and approval for funding by the MB. Members are available to participate in regular and ad hoc meetings and to communicate their knowledge to PARC and information from PARC to their broad range of international contacts. The IB will work in close collaboration with Task 3.3 (Networking and Synergies) and all other WPs to promote the interaction between other major scientific initiatives and PARC and to facilitate the uptake of PARC results internationally.

2. Selection process for the SF and IB members

2.1 Development of criteria for the SF

In order to set up the SF, criteria to assess appropriate organizations following their application to become members of the SF were developed. These criteria were discussed within WP3, with the PARC Coordination Team (CT) and agreed upon by the MB.

These criteria were integrated into an online questionnaire that contained a short introduction on PARC and the SF nomination process. The criteria comprised:

- the expression of interest;
 - indication of area of engagement (human health/risk assessment, human biomonitoring, occupational health/risk assessment, environmental risk assessment, environmental monitoring, new approach methodologies, risk communication, science to policy);
- description of organization (type of organization, number of Member States and organizations represented, national centres);
- commitment to the SF (to participate in annual meetings and consultations);
- institutional interest and details for information (organization's name, contact person, level of expertise, representation in external boards/working groups,...).

Finally, the questionnaire (Annex 6.1) was distributed as an Open Call on October, 4 2022. The call developed via MS forms survey was open for four weeks.

2.2 Development of criteria for the IB

Given the role of the IB within PARC, after consultation with the WP3 partners, the following criteria have been proposed:

1. Relevance to PARC

- Expertise (with a particular focus on medical expertise/background and/or chemical risk assessment) (YES/NO);
- Availability to participate in the work of the IB, attend its meetings and contribute to the working groups, with the required continuity (YES/NO);
- Experience* in multidisciplinary scientific project management;
- Experience* in managing scientific projects in one of the areas within PARC;
- Experience* in scientific communication;
- Experience* in scientific assessment and/or provision of scientific advice to risk managers;
- Experience* in carrying out scientific risk assessment and/or providing scientific advice in fields related to chemicals and environment, human exposure, HBM, hazard assessment, risk assessment;
- Experience* in the development of relevant EU policies as part of duties for:
 - the European Commission,
 - the European Parliament,
 - the Council of the EU.

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- Experience* in reviewing scientific work and ability to analyse complex information in the area.

*For all experience related questions, the following classes have been proposed: Long experience (<20 years); Moderate experience (10-20 years); Limited experience (>10 years); None.

2. Scientific qualifications

- Prizes and awards (number, #);
- Distinguished fellowships or memberships in prestigious academic circles or in high-ranking committees, bodies, academies, etc. (#);
- Independently raised funding;
- EU (FPs, HORIZON, COST, LIFE) projects coordinated (#);
- Width of networks (# of people included);
- Relevant papers in scientific journals (#), (>60), up to 150 accounted for*;
- Citations (#) (>2500)*;
- h-index (#) (>30)*;
- Number of patents (#);
- Invitations to conference talks (#).

*Considered outstanding scientific qualifications.

3. Other supporting information

- Experience in international organization (YES/NO);
- Rank in international organizations ("Director" or "Head of Unit" or "Team Leader" or "None");
- Held visiting professor positions (#);
- Social commitment and engagement (YES/NO);
- Involvement in research, university and scientific committees (#).

These criteria were used to develop a specific CV format to be completed by the candidates (presented in Annex 6.2).

2.3 Development of an algorithm for evaluating the candidate profiles

2.3.1 Development of the algorithm for evaluating the IB candidate profiles and selection process

In order to evaluate the profile of the candidates, an algorithm that allows the assessment of categorical and numerical values in a unified manner has been developed. This algorithm with slight adaptations was equally used for a screening of the candidates of the SF (see below).

The algorithm has been implemented in Microsoft Excel; all categorical values could be selected by drop-down menu cells, while the numerical values (e.g. number of papers) were introduced by the user. For every categorical

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value, a score was assigned, while for each numerical value, a "normalization" coefficient was assigned. These assignments are presented in the Tables of Annex 6.3.

These weighing factors can be modified, based on the relative weight that one would like to give to the selection criteria. For the needs of the IB selection, the weights were adjusted as presented in Annex 6.3.

A tiered approach was followed for ranking and selecting the IB members:

- Initially, a list of candidates had been proposed through a PARC consortium survey. That list was further enriched by additional candidates proposed by the PARC WP3 team, as well as by the PARC CT and MB.
- All candidates were invited to send their CV in a specific format (Annex 6.2) that corresponded to the questions of the criteria and their translation into the algorithm.
- The information extracted from the CV was introduced in the algorithm, and a total score, comprised by the partial scores of the (a) relevance, (b) excellence and (c) other supporting information was calculated for each candidate.
- A final qualitative assessment was performed to ensure a balanced coverage of thematic areas of PARC.

2.3.2 Adaptation of the algorithm for evaluating the SF candidate profiles and the selection process

Similarly to the IB evaluation process, an algorithm that accounted for both qualitative and quantitative criteria was developed. However, it has to be noted, that the weights for the criteria are different, since academic criteria (e.g. publications and citations) are not relevant for the SF (Annex 6.4, regarding the weights applied to criteria of the applicants).

A two-step-approach was followed for ranking the candidate Organizations:

□ First, an algorithm based on area of engagement, commitment to the Stakeholder Forum, and information on the Organization was applied and the Organizations were sorted based on their score.

□ At a second step criteria to ensure a well-balanced composition of SF members were applied. These criteria included broadening the distribution of stakeholder type and area of expertise/interest represented in the SF and ensuring its balance in terms of Industry vs NGOs, wide representation via important associations and the coverage of the different thematic areas of PARC.

3. Process for the SF and IB members selection

3.1 Final outcomes of the SF selection process

3.1.1 Results of the call

The call reached around 100 institutions from a stakeholder list that included interested organizations, and representative umbrella organizations known to PARC or those identified based on experience with the HBM4EU Stakeholder Forum. The list was reviewed and additional stakeholders to represent the broad thematic area of PARC were included.

Responses from 40 applicants were received within the deadline of the call, of which 34 expressed their interest to become a member of the PARC SF. The remaining six applicants wished to stay in contact with PARC and

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receive information throughout the project duration and will be considered as interested stakeholders for the broader PARC stakeholder community.

3.1.2 Proposed candidates for the SF (Dec 2022)

After application of the two-step approach for ranking the candidate Organizations, the following list was proposed and approved by the MB and GSB:

1. Eurometaux
2. EEB (European Environmental Bureau)
3. CFE (Cruelty Free Europe)
4. CropLife Europe
5. Cefic (European Chemical Industry Council)
6. Plastics Europe
7. EnvMed (European Network for Environmental Medicine)
8. DUCC (Downstream Users of Chemicals Co-ordination Group)
9. Chem Trust
10. ETUI (European Trade Union Institute)
11. WECF France
12. EFA (European Federation of Allergy and Airways Diseases Patients' Associations)
13. Cosmetics Europe
14. Food Packaging Forum
15. SMEunited

Figure 1 depicts the PARC SF members by stakeholder type, while more details regarding the final proposed list are presented in

Table 1.

Figure 1. Proposed PARC SF members per stakeholder type

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Table 1. SF - Selection — final proposed list — December 2022

Organisation	SH Type (initially applied as)	SH Type (adjusted)	Area of Expertise	Region covered	Former HBM4EU SF member	Justification
Eurometaux	Industry/Industry Association	Industry/Industry Association	interface Industry & Research	27more	X	European Metal industry
EEB (European Environmental Bureau)	NGO	NGO	EU chemicals legislation	27more	X	Major environmental NGO – representative of civic society
CFE (Cruelty Free Europe)	NGO	NGO	use of non-animal methods	6-26		Non-animal approaches
CropLife Europe	Association/Other	Industry/Industry Association	agriculture, pesticides	27more		Pesticides industry
Cefic (European Chemical Industry Council)	Industry/Industry Association	Industry/Industry Association	biomonitoring (eg occupational), NAMs and modernized risk assessment frameworks	27more	X	Chemicals industry
Plastics Europe	Industry/Industry Association	Industry/Industry Association	industry & research, packaging & plastics	27more	X (since 2019)	Plastics industry
EnvMed (European Network for Environmental Medicine)	NGO	NGO	environmental medicine	6-26		Environmental health
DUCC (Downstream Users of Chemicals Co-ordination Group)	Industry/Industry Association	Industry/Industry Association	chemical industry, chemical safety assessments under REACH	27more	X	Downstream users
Chem Trust	NGO	NGO	prevention of synthetic chemicals from causing long term damage to wildlife or humans	0-5	X	Environmental health, chemical risk assessment
ETUI (European Trade Union Institute)	Association/Other	Association/other	workers' interests at European level	27more	X	Workers interest

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Organisation	SH Type (initially applied as)	SH Type (adjusted)	Area of Expertise	Region covered	Former HBM4EU SF member	Justification
WECF France	NGO	NGO	environmental health and gender	0-5	X	Environment & gender, NGO,
EFA (European Federation of Allergy and Airways Diseases Patients' Associations)	NGO	NGO	patient community, medicine	27more	X	Patient organisation
Cosmetics Europe	Association/Other	Industry/Industry Association	cosmetics industry	6-26		Cosmetics Industry
Food Packaging Forum	NGO	NGO	support Scientific research and science-policy communication in the field of chemical hazard identification and risk assessment	6-26		Food Packaging Research
SMEunited	Association/Other	Association/other	effects for SMEs	27more	X	Small & medium enterprises

3.2 Final outcomes of the IB selection process

3.2.1 Completion of candidates list

A total number of 34 candidates were identified by PARC members, as listed below.

Candidates proposed through the PARC Survey:

1. Ana Witt, Head of Unit, United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP), Chemicals Knowledge and Risks team.
2. Abiola Olanipekun, Chief of the Science and Technical Assistance Branch at the Basel, Rotterdam and Stockholm Conventions (BRS).
3. Jacqueline Alvarez, Chief of the UNEP Economy Division's Chemicals and Health Branch.
4. Richard Brown, World Health Organization (WHO) Chemical Risk Assessment Network.
5. Maria Neira, high level representative of WHO.
6. Jean-Charles Leblanc (Anses).
7. Antonia Calafat, Chief of the Organic Analytical Toxicology Branch at the Division of Laboratory Sciences, National Center for Environmental Health of the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC).
8. Bjorn Hansen, European Chemicals Agency (ECHA).
9. Dorota Jarosinska, WHO.
10. Sebastian Oberthür, Director of the Research Centre for Environment, Economy and Energy, and Professor for Environment and Sustainable Development at the Brussels School of Governance.
11. Shoji Nakayama, lead exposure scientist for the Japan Environment and Children's Study (JECS) and head of the Exposure Dynamics Research Section, Centre for Health and Environmental Risk Research, National Institute for Environmental Studies, Japan.
12. Katrine Borgå, researcher in the Borgå research group, advisor to the Norwegian Environmental Specimen Bank.
13. Eeva Leinala.
14. Carolyn Vickers, Head of Chemical Safety and Health Unit at WHO.
15. Irina Zastenskaya, WHO.
16. Patience Brown, policy analyst (chemicals) at Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).
17. Thomas Jakl, former chair of the ECHA's Management board and Deputy Director General of the Austrian Environment Ministry responsible for Chemicals Policy.

Candidates proposed by WP3 members, PARC CT and PARC MB

18. Heather Wallace, Emeritus Professor of Biochemical Pharmacology and Toxicology, Editor in Chief of Toxicology Research.
19. Karel A.C. De Schamphelaere, Ghent University Environmental Toxicology unit (GhEnToxLab).
20. Greet Schoeters, ex program manager of environmental health at VITO and Emeritus Professor at the Department of Biomedical Sciences of the University of Antwerp.

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21. Russel Thomas, Director of the US-EPA Center for Computational Toxicology and Exposure (CCTE).
22. Suzanne Fitzpatrick, Senior Advisor for Toxicology FDA's Center for Food Safety and Applied Nutrition (CFSAN).
23. Vasilis Vasiliou, Chair of the Department of Environmental Health Sciences, Yale University.
24. Dag Ellingsen, Research Director, National Institute of Occupational Health in Norway.
25. Thomas Hartung, Director of the Center for Alternatives to Animal Testing (CAAT), Professor at Johns Hopkins University Bloomberg School of Public Health.
26. Jaroslav Slobodnik, chairman of NORMAN Association.
27. Hanna-Andrea Rother, Head of Environmental Health Division, University Cape town.
28. Blanca Serrano Ramon, Secretary General of European Center for Ecotoxicology and Toxicology of Chemicals (ECETOC).
29. An Van Nieuwenhuysse, Elected member of the Board of Directors, Strategy Counselor, International Society on Exposure Science (ISES), European Chapter.
30. Nineta Hrastelj, Secretary General, European Chemical Society (EuChemS).
31. Anni St-Amand, Section Head, National Biomonitoring, Health Canada.
32. Douglas Haines, Head and science advisor in Health Canada's Healthy Environments and Consumer Safety Branch.
33. Bob Diderich, head of environment, health and safety programme at the OECD.
34. Anne Gourmelon, leader of the OECD Test Guidelines Programme.

3.2.2 Invitation to provide their CVs and to be candidates for the PARC IB

After the completion of the list, invitation emails were sent to all of them, together with a specific CV format to be completed (ANNEX 6.2).

A deadline of 21 days had been provided to the proposed candidates, to respond and return the completed forms. From the 34 proposed candidates:

- Eleven (11) candidates did not respond at all, despite the several reminders sent.
- Four (4) have declined the invitation, due to institutional restrictions.
- Four (4) have responded positively, but never sent the CV form.
- Fifteen (15) candidates have responded positively and have sent the CV form.

The OECD colleagues who have been proposed as possible members of the IB, after internal consultation amongst them, came back designating Dr. Diderich as the actual candidate, with the understanding that all of them would be available to support the work of the IB, yet without becoming a formal member of the Board.

Colleagues from UN entities, such as WHO, FAO, UNEP have responded that although very interested in the work of PARC, they could not join as formal members of the IB, because of UN policy to avoid such appointments in view of 360o independence. They confirmed, however, that they would be available to support and follow the work of PARC by participating in the works of the IB as observers.

3.2.3 Evaluation and final decision

After the collection of the CV forms, the information for each candidate, was introduced in the algorithm, and the total score, comprised by the partial scores of the (a) relevance, (b) excellence and (c) other supporting information has been delivered, as illustrated in Figure 2, presented in a random order.

All proposed candidates, were considered as mutually complementing the needs for thematic, institutional and jurisdictional completeness of the IB. Thus, with the agreement of the MB, the WP3 members agreed to propose the inclusion of all the 15 candidates, as presented in Table 2. These candidates were also presented to and approved by the GSB.

Candidates who had expressed interest to be part of the PARC IB, but due to commitments were not able to participate at the current stage, have been considered for involvement later. In addition, Task 3.1b partners are continuously updating list of potential candidates/reserves, so as to ensure the smooth operation of the IB.

Figure 2. Evaluation of the candidates (presented in random order) based on the collected information through the dedicated CV forms

Table 2. Final list of candidates for the IB

Name	Institution	Gender	Institution country	Country of origin	Expertise relevant to PARC
Thomas Hartung	Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health	M	USA	Germany	NAMs, alternative methods, multi-omics approaches, bioinformatics
Vasilis Vasiliou	Yale School of Public Health	M	USA	Greece	Omics, human cohorts, biomonitoring
Douglas Haines	Health Canada (retired)	M	Canada	Canada	Biomonitoring, exposure and risk assessment
Jaroslav Slobodnik	NORMAN network	M	EU	Slovakia	EWS, chemicals monitoring
Russell S. Thomas	US EPA	M	USA	USA	Toxicology, high-throughput screening
Suzanne Fitzpatrick	US FDA	F	USA	USA	NAMS, risk assessment

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Annie St-Amand	Health Canada	F	Canada	Canada	Biomonitoring, exposure and risk assessment
Greet Schoeters	University of Antwerp	F	Belgium	Belgium	Biomonitoring, toxicology, risk assessment
Hanna-Andrea Rother	University of Cape Town	F	South Africa	USA	Policy, regulatory and implementation of chemical risk assessment
Diderich Robert	OECD	M	International, HQ in France	Luxemburg	NAMs, QSARs, exposure assessment
Antonia M. Calafat	U.S. CDC	F	USA	Spain	Biomonitoring, cohorts, exposure assessment
Nineta Hrastelj	EuChemS	F	EU	Slovenia	Chemistry, chemicals safety
Dag Ellingsen	National Institute of Occupational Health Norway	M	Norway	Norway	Toxicology, biomonitoring and risk assessment
Shoji F. Nakayama	National Institute for Environmental Studies - Japan	M	Japan	Japan	Biomonitoring, cohorts, exposure assessment
Blanca Serrano Ramon	ECETOC	F	Belgium	Spain	Toxicology, biochemistry

4. Implementation procedure

4.1 Implementation of the SF

The two-stage selection process of the members of the Stakeholder Forum included consideration of a broader spread of stakeholder types and areas of expertise/interest represented in the SF, as well as ensuring a balance between industry and NGOs, broad representation from key associations, and coverage of PARC's various topic areas. Preference was also given to umbrella organizations and organizations operating in many EU countries. After approval of the SF composition by the PARC Boards, the following steps were taken: :

- (a) the approved candidate organizations have been informed (see 4.1.2) by email on their acceptance and on the terms of reference for their participation.
- (b) The 1st SF was conducted on February 28th 2023 via teleconference.
- (c) the internal structure and working collaboration of the SF as well as their needs has been discussed at the 1st SF (agenda and draft TOR attached)

The SF will be held annually and needed additional meetings will be discussed and defined with the SF members. After 2-3 years, the performance of the SF members will be evaluated with the option to make changes, also in terms of membership.

The organisations which expressed their interest but were not selected to become member of the SF have been informed about the selection procedure and were invited to join the broader PARC stakeholder community and possibly SYNnet.

4.2 Implementation of the IB

The next steps after the approval of the IB members by the PARC Boards will be to:

- (a) Inform the candidates of the final decision, setting up of the IB and of the respective terms of reference for their participation in detail.
- (b) Set the date/time for the first meeting of the PARC IB; the meeting will be held via teleconference in the course of February 2023.
- (c) Organise the internal structure and workings of the IB
- (d) Inform the IB on the structure and the current state of progress of the PARC workplan.

Regular meetings are planned to take place. It was further noted that given the wide spectrum of activities and themes of the PARC projects, a re-evaluation of the IB composition will take place during year 3 of the PARC implementation with a view to potentially adapt the Board configuration on the basis of the needs for skills, competence and international coverage of the IB at that point in time. The process that will be followed then, will be similar to the one followed now and described herein.

5. Annex

5.1 Questionnaire from SF Open Call

PARC Stakeholder Forum - Open Call for Participation

The 7-year Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC), running from 2022-2029 with an indicative budget of 400m EUR, has started in May under Horizon Europe and is seeking to develop next-generation chemical risk assessment in order to protect health and the environment and support the European Green Deal.

PARC offers interested stakeholders the opportunity to participate and actively engage in the Stakeholder Forum (SF) of the partnership. The members of the Stakeholder Forum are expected to contribute with feedback and input, in order to maximize the benefits and advantages of PARC, both for achieving PARC objectives as well as for their own activities with similar objectives.

In the PARC Stakeholder Forum, it is of importance to have representatives from different parts of society, covering provision, use and potential impact of chemicals in society, as well as the production and use of knowledge. Thus, if you are a stakeholder, who is interested in risk assessment of chemicals and/or involved in risk communication or familiar with science to public or science to policy interactions - we cordially invite you to respond to this call.

As member of the Stakeholder Forum, you will be involved in regular interactions with the PARC consortium and stakeholder representatives through annual Stakeholder Forum meetings in PARC. More intense mutual exchange will be possible and is encouraged through ad hoc (online) meetings and consultations.

The Stakeholder Forum builds on the experience from HBM4EU, the European Human Biomonitoring Initiative. The PARC Stakeholder Forum offers to the stakeholders the possibility for interaction, i.e. regular communication, targeted information and continuous exchange on PARC's process and current developments in chemical risk assessment of human health and the environment. The PARC Stakeholder Forum will hold a maximum of 15 members.

Following the open call, the selection process for future stakeholder members will be based on the criteria defined below while also ensuring complementarity in expertise and broad coverage of interests.

A final list of members to constitute the PARC Stakeholder Forum will be achieved in November 2022. The first online meeting is scheduled for December 2022/early January 2023.

Looking forward to your proposal of interest,

with kind regards

PARC WP3.1a Stakeholder Forum task leaders & partners

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Expectations and goals for stakeholders in PARC

The Stakeholder Forum in PARC should contribute to the following goals:

- * to foster collaboration and synergies with stakeholders from NGOs, academia, industry/business associations, employer and worker representative bodies and consumer organisations
- * to provide regular information on current developments or concerns in relation to chemical risk assessment of human health and the environment to the Management Board (MB) and Governing Board (GB) of PARC
- * to provide feedback and input on performance indicators of PARC[1], priorities and key elements of PARC
- * to boost the impact of PARC through dissemination of knowledge and interaction with stakeholders to enhance the uptake of results and communication to different audiences
- * to co-create a living and sustainable Partnership, seeking both to promote and to benefit from mutual interests, needs and priorities as well as strategic and technical aspects to ensure the progress of chemical risk assessment
- * to enhance the accountability and credibility of the activities and results of the Partnership.

Please outline your motivation to contribute to the PARC Stakeholder Forum goals (3-5 sentences):

Expression of interest according to criteria

Please indicate the area of engagement of your institution:

	1= not applicable	2= slightly not applicable	3= slightly applicable	4= most applicable
Area of Engagement				
Human health / risk assessment				
Human Biomonitoring				
Occupational health				
Environmental risk assessment				
Environmental Monitoring				
New approach methodologies				
Risk communication				
Science to policy				
Other/ please specify:				

Please describe your ambitions to facilitate and support to disseminate PARC activities and findings related to:

Communication tools	
Target groups	
Channels	
No of followers	

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Please describe your organization

Type of organization (industry, NGO, other)	
Number of Member states involved	
Number of organizations represented	
Do you have any national centers? If so where?	

Options to participate as Stakeholder in PARC

Please select the following option on how to participate within the PARC project?

- PARC-Stakeholder Forum (commit to annual meetings (2-3/year) and consultations (2-3/year), - continual & sustainable participation)
 - PARC interested Stakeholder (information via events, newsletters, trainings, webinars, website...)
-

Institutional interest and details for information

Name of Organisation/Institution

Contact Name and Role in the Organisation

Level of Expertise (Number of years of experience/engagement in the field)

- Long experience (>20 years)
- Moderate experience (10-20 years)
- Limited experience (<10 years)
- None

Position in Organisation: Are you representing the organization in external boards and/or working groups

YES NO

Contact Email(s)

Please provide a short paragraph/information on your organization's benefits to become a member of the Stakeholder Forum:

Your answers have been saved. Thank you for your input!

☑ PARC- indicators of success will monitor the output and impact of PARC

5.2 CV format that was send to the PARC IB proposed candidates

European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals PARC

Please place a photo of yours here (optional)

Name and surname:
Email:
Telephone(s):
Place of birth:
Date of birth:
Current position:

Professional experience

Education

Please describe your expertise in relevance to PARC (350 words max)

Will you be able to commit to PARC International Board obligations? (please provide a statement of 250 words max)

Relevance to PARC

Experience in multidisciplinary scientific project management

Please indicate your experience and provide a justification (250 words max).

- Long experience (>20 years)
- Moderate experience (10-20 years)
- Limited experience (<10 years)
- None

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Experience in managing scientific projects in one of the areas within PARC

Please indicate your experience and provide a justification (250 words max).

- Long experience (>20 years)
- Moderate experience (10-20 years)
- Limited experience (<10 years)
- None

Experience in scientific communication

Please indicate your experience and provide a justification (250 words max).

- Long experience (>20 years)
- Moderate experience (10-20 years)
- Limited experience (<10 years)
- None

Experience in scientific assessment and/or provision of scientific advice to risk managers

Please indicate your experience and provide a justification (250 words max).

- Long experience (>20 years)
- Moderate experience (10-20 years)
- Limited experience (<10 years)
- None

Experience in carrying out scientific risk assessment and/or providing scientific advice in fields related to chemicals and environment, human exposure, HBM, hazard assessment, risk assessment

Please indicate your experience and provide a justification (250 words max).

- Long experience (>20 years)
- Moderate experience (10-20 years)
- Limited experience (<10 years)
- None

Experience in managing scientific projects in one of the areas within PARC

Please indicate your experience and provide a justification (250 words max).

- Long experience (>20 years)
- Moderate experience (10-20 years)
- Limited experience (<10 years)
- None

Experience in scientific communication

Please indicate your experience and provide a justification (250 words max).

- Long experience (>20 years)
- Moderate experience (10-20 years)
- Limited experience (<10 years)
- None

Experience in scientific assessment and/or provision of scientific advice to risk managers

Please indicate your experience and provide a justification (250 words max).

- Long experience (>20 years)
- Moderate experience (10-20 years)
- Limited experience (<10 years)
- None

Experience in carrying out scientific risk assessment and/or providing scientific advice in fields related to chemicals and environment, human exposure, HBM, hazard assessment, risk assessment

Please indicate your experience and provide a justification (250 words max).

- Long experience (>20 years)
- Moderate experience (10-20 years)
- Limited experience (<10 years)
- None

Experience in the development of relevant EU policies as part of duties for

- the European Commission

- the European Parliament

- the Council of the EU

Please indicate your experience and provide a justification (250 words max).

- Long experience (>20 years)
- Moderate experience (10-20 years)
- Limited experience (<10 years)
- None

Experience in reviewing scientific work and ability to analyse complex information in the area

Please indicate your experience and provide a justification (250 words max).

- Long experience (>20 years)
- Moderate experience (10-20 years)
- Limited experience (<10 years)
- None

Scientific excellence

Prizes and awards

Please provide a numbered list of your prizes and awards

1.
2.

Distinguished fellowships or memberships in prestigious academic circles or in high-ranking committees, bodies, academies, etc.

Please provide a numbered list of your Distinguished fellowships or memberships in prestigious academic circles or in high-ranking committees, bodies, academies, etc.

1.
2.

Independently raised funding

Please provide a list with the amount of independently raised funding that you have brought to your organization in Millions (euro) of funding.

1. Project Name 1 / amount for the Organisation
2. Project Name 2 / amount for the Organisation
3.

Number of EU (FPs, HORIZON, COST, LIFE) projects coordinated

Please provide a list with the EU (FPs, HORIZON, COST, LIFE) projects coordinated.

1. Project Name 1 / Organisation
2. Project Name 2 / Organisation
3.

Width of networks

Please provide an indication (from the selected categories) of the width of network that you are connected, and briefly describe (250 words max) its activity and relevance to PARC.

- More than 5000 scientists
- More than 1000 scientists
- More than 200 scientists

Number of relevant papers in scientific journals

Please provide a numbered list with the relevant papers in scientific journals.

1. Paper 1
2. Paper 2
3.

Number of citations

Please provide the number of citations in the various scientific networks (at least one).

1. Scholar
2. PubMed
3. Scopus
4. Academia
5. Research Gate

h-index

Please provide your h-index in the various scientific networks (at least one).

1. Scholar
2. PubMed
3. Scopus
4. Academia
5. Research Gate

Number of patents

Please provide a numbered list with the relevant patents.

1. Patent 1
2. Patent 2
3.

Number of invitation to conference talks

Please provide a numbered list with the invitation to conference talks.

1. Title of talk 2/ conference name, place and date 1
2. Title of talk 2/ conference name, place and date 2
3.

Other supporting information

Experience in international organisation

Have you ever worked in an international organization (e.g. WHO, IARC, JRC, e.t.c)? if yes define the briefly the period and the role (250 words max).

Rank in international organisations

Please provide information about your rank in the hierarchy of the international organization among the following options, and then provide some details on the organization and the period:

- Director
- Head of Unit
- Team Leader

- None

Held visiting professor positions

Please provide a numbered list with the visiting professor positions held.

- Position 1 / University, place and date 1
- Position 2 / University, place and date 2
-

Social commitment and engagement

Please provide a brief description of your social commitment and engagement (max 250 words).

Involvement in research, university and scientific committees

Please provide a numbered list with your involvement in research, university and scientific committees.

- Committee 1 / Institution, place and date 1
- Committee 1 / Institution, place and date 1
-

Additional information

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5.3 Weights used for the various criteria and their respective classification for the IB

Relevance to PARC															
YES/NO	YES/NO	Experience class		Experience class		Experience class		Experience class		Experience class		Experience class		Experience class	
Expertise (with a particular focus on medical expertise/background)	Availability to participate in the work of the International Board, attend its meetings and contribute to the working groups, with the required continuity	Experience in multidisciplinary scientific project management		Experience in managing scientific projects in one of the areas within PARC		Experience in scientific communication		Experience in scientific assessment and/or provision of scientific advice to risk managers		Experience in carrying out scientific risk assessment and/or providing scientific advice in fields related to chemicals and environment, human exposure, HBM, hazard assessment, risk assessment		Experience in the development of relevant EU policies as part of duties for - the European Commission, - the European Parliament, - the Council of the EU.		Experience in reviewing scientific work and ability to analyse complex information in the area	
1	1	Long experience	300	Long experience	300	Long experience	300	Long experience	1000	Long experience	1500	Long experience	1500	Long experience	300
0	0	Moderate experience	100	Moderate experience	100	Moderate experience	100	Moderate experience	500	Moderate experience	750	Moderate experience	750	Moderate experience	100
		Limited experience	50	Limited experience	50	Limited experience	50	Limited experience	200	Limited experience	250	Limited experience	250	Limited experience	50
		None	0	None	0	None	0	None	0	None	0	None	0	None	0

Long experience: (>20 years)

Moderate experience: (10-20 years)

Limited experience: (<10 years)

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Scientific excellence										
#	#	M€ - in Millions (euro) of funding	#	# of people included		#, (>60), up to 150 accounted for	#, (>2500)	#, (>30)	#	#
Prizes and awards	Distinguished fellowships or memberships in prestigious academic circles or in high-ranking committees, bodies, academies, etc.	Independently raised funding	EU (FPs, HORIZON, COST, LIFE) projects coordinated	Width of networks		Relevant papers in scientific journals	Citations	h-index	Number of patents	Invitations to conference talks
100	50	100	100	More than 5000 scientists	1000	5	0.5	10	100	10
				More than 1000 scientists	300					
				More than 200 scientists	100					
				None	0					

Other supporting information					
YES/NO	"Director" or "Head of Unit" or "Team Leader" or "None"		#	YES/NO	#
Experience in international organisation	Rank in international organisations		Held visiting professor positions	Social commitment and engagement	Involvement in research, university and scientific committees
500	Director	2500	100	150	100

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0	Head of Unit	1000		0	
	Team Leader	500			
	None	0			

5.4 Weights applied to criteria of the SF applicants

category	criteria	response score
experience	Long experience (>20 years)	1000
experience	Moderate experience (10-20 years)	750
experience	Limited experience (<10 years)	500
experience	None	250
organisation type	Industry/Industry Association	1
organisation type	NGO	1
organisation type	Association/Other	1
organisation type	Research	1
organisation type	Agency (EEB...)	1
organisation type	Company	1
position	Secretary General/ General director/Chair	1000
position	Policy Advisor	1000
position	Managing/Operations Director/CEO	500
position	Head of.../Scientific director/Coordinator of...	500
position	Senior expert	500
area of engagement	most applicable	1000
area of engagement	slightly applicable	750
area of engagement	slightly not applicable	500
area of engagement	not applicable	250
PARC relevance_SF	YES	1
PARC relevance_SF (interested stakeholder)	NO	0
no of members states involved	27more	750
no of members states involved	6-26	500
no of members states involved	0-5	250
representative_role	YES	2000
representative_role	NO	0
national_centers	YES	500
national_centers	NO	0

5.4 Agenda of the 1st SF

1st

PARC

Stakeholder

Forum

28.2.2023

9:30 -12:30 MS teams meeting

Time	Agenda	Materials	Responsibilities
9:30-10:05	Get-together tour de table: Introduction	PPT – Welcome, Members list, PARC SF goals	Chair, EAA
10:05-10:35	PARC Coordination team (CT): Introduction on SH Participation within PARC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Introduction to PARC objectives ✓ goals/targets of SF activities ✓ activities relevant for SH in 1st year of PARC 	PPT – PARC overview, focus on SH involvement	PARC CT – Pascal Sanders
10:35-11:05	Expectations and Needs of Stakeholders Discussion	Whiteboard activity	Chair, EAA
11:05 - 11:15 Coffee BREAK			
11:15-11:40	Our Work in the SF: Terms of Reference <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ PARC SF task leaders can use the input provided of SF members and develop final version of Terms of Reference 	PPT –Terms of Reference	EAA & SF Partner
11:40-12:00	Our Work in the SF: chairing the SF <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Introduction to role and perception of Chair & Co-Chair in the Stakeholder Forum ✓ Suggestion to vote for 1SF member to become chair for the following annual meeting 	Based on information on chair selection in invitation email	EAA & SF partner
12:00-12:10	Communication in 2023 and Topics of 2nd SF <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ How do SF members wish to stay in contact? ✓ Uptake of PARC relevant input for discussion in SF meeting ✓ Additional online meeting? Email information via chair 		EAA & SF partner

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12:10-12:25	Introduction of International Board (IB) & status update, exchange with SF		WP3 IB task leaders: Denis Sarigiannis & Spyros Karakitsios
12:25-12:30	Final Wrap-up & Goodbye		EAA & SF partner

Any further information on the agenda of the 1st Stakeholder Forum in PARC can be received from

The WP3 Stakeholder Forum task leaders of PARC

Daniela Zanini-Freitag

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& Maria Uhl

maria.uhl@umweltbundesamt.at

WP3 co-leaders

Maria João Silva (INSA)

Sónia Namorado (INSA)

Aglaiia Koutsodimou (GCSL)

Eugenia Dessipri (GCSL)

ARC WP3 SF task partners:

Ana Virgolino, Aristidis Tsatsakis, Bojana Zegura, Hans Christian Stolzenberg, Isabel Moura, Kari Larssen-Aas, Mojca Drobnic, Nikiforos Alygizakis, Niki Maragou, Nikolaos Thomaidis, Osvaldo Rodrigues Santos, Polychronis Stivaktakis, Roser Gasol, Sture Rolfheim Bye

5.5 Draft Terms of Reference for the SF

Terms of Reference of the Stakeholder Forum in PARC
(draft version: Feb20 2023)

1. Source of Terms

PARC as the 7-year Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals ([PARC](#)), running from 2022-2029 with an indicative budget of 400m EUR, has started in May 2022 under Horizon Europe. The project is seeking to develop next-generation chemical risk assessment in order to protect human health and the environment and to support the European Green Deal.

Interested Stakeholders were provided the opportunity to apply in order to participate and actively engage in the Stakeholder Forum (SF) of the partnership. The selection of members of the SF has followed a decision-making procedure following an open call in October 2022.

The SF is appointed by the Grant Signatory Board (GSB) – upon proposal of WP3 and after agreement of the Management Board (MB) and Governing Board (GB). The PARC Stakeholder Forum, as described in the PARC grant agreement holds a maximum of 15 members and accompanies PARC for the duration of 7 years.

2. Activities

The PARC Stakeholder Forum shall

- ✓ facilitate interaction, i.e., regular communication, targeted information and continuous exchange on PARC's process and current developments in chemical risk assessment of human health and the environment with relevant European stakeholders.

The Stakeholder Forum shall give advice to the Governing Board & the Management Board on the conduct of the PARC Partnership, relevant projects and activities within the project.

3. Composition

Fifteen representatives from bodies and stakeholder organisations operating at EU level build the Stakeholder Forum.

Eurometaux (Violaine Verougstraete), EEB-European Environmental Bureau (Helene Loonen), CFE- Cruelty Free Europe (Emma Grange), CropLife Europe (Stephanie Nadzialek), Cefic-European Chemical Industry Council (Katia Lacasse), Plastics Europe (Patrik Müller), EnvMed- European Network for Environmental Medicine (Florian Schulze), DUCC- Downstream Users of Chemicals Co-ordination Group (Giulia Sebastio), CHEM Trust (Ninja Reineke), ETUI-European Trade Union Institute (Tony Musu), WECF France (Sylvie Platel), EFA- European Federation of Allergy and Airways Diseases Patients' Associations (Artur Badyda), Cosmetics Europe (Veronique Poulsen), Food Packaging Forum (Birgit Geueke) & SMEunited (Marko Susnik).

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Nomination and selection of two Vice-chairs of the Stakeholder Forum

The PARC grant agreement foresees the selection of two Vice-chairs for the Stakeholder Forum. The Vice-chair1 will represent the members of the Stakeholder Forum and will chair the joint meetings. Another Vice-chair should support the Vice-chair and both of them are nominated for the first annual period with the option to extend the chairing period every year throughout the partnership.

The SF consists of **15 institutions with different interests** from sectors such as "Industry/Industry associations", "Associations/Other", and "NGOs". It is desirable that **each of the selected Vice-chair represents different interests in a balanced manner.**

As a result of the nomination process the Stakeholder Forum selected 2 candidates to hold Vice-chairs position. A Suppléant to the Vice Chairs will be decided upon the SF work package task partners of PARC. The nomination reflects in an ideal way a balance between the above-mentioned sectors of interests. This proposal relies on experience from the HBM4EU Stakeholder Forum and shall be established in a similar manner in the PARC Partnership. The SF organisational structure is supported by the Project Coordinator, the Management Board and stays in close exchange with the processing of the International Board in PARC.

Following the first Stakeholder Forum in PARC, held online in February 2023 the elected two positions of Vice-Chairs are:

Vice-Chair: **Violaine Verzougstrate,** **Eurometaux**_____represents industry
(supporter: Katia Lacasse, Cefic)

Vice-Chair2: **Emma Grange, CFE** represents NGOs

Suppléant: **SF Task leader & rotation of SF Work Package3 Task Partners**

4. Working Methods

The first kick off meeting is held in February 2023. The Forum will convene annually. When applicable the meetings will be held back-to-back with the Governing Board physical meetings. The dates of these annual meetings shall be announced as early as possible, as soon as date for Governing Board (GB) meeting is agreed. The agenda will be sent out 21 calendar days before the meeting with the possibility to add agenda items up to 7 calendar days before the meeting.

Stakeholders are encouraged to engage themselves actively through forum meetings, workshops and written requests for input.

The minutes of the stakeholder forum shall be drafted within 15 calendar days, feedback from stakeholders shall be provided within 15 days after sending. The minutes are considered as accepted after 15 calendar days following receipt of the final version.

Decisions are binding once the relevant parts of the minutes have been accepted. After acceptance, the minutes will be sent out to all members of the Stakeholder Forum, Consortium Body (Management Board) and to the PARC Coordination team.

A summary of the minutes with the most relevant, non-confidential issues covered in the recent SF meeting will be published in the following PARC's newsletter. SF members will be asked to sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement (**under preparation**) to ensure the confidentiality of the PARC information.

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SF members will be granted access to a shared workspace on the PARC sharepoint (closed library, **under preparation**) in order to share documents and information.

5. Confidentiality and Conflicts of Interest

PARC provides a communication and dissemination strategy that describes the general standards of PARC communication including rules, procedures and policies for external communication: Confidentiality on both internal and external communication and members therefore will carefully safeguard all confidential information (for e.g., discussion or preliminary results, on-going decision-making processes). Additionally, to that, transparency on internal and external communication will be mandatory and includes the PARC sharepoint for internal communication (**under preparation**) and the website for formal documents publicly available.

6. Duration of the terms

The Terms of Reference are valid for 3 years and shall be re-evaluated after 3 years, with the option to make changes, also in terms of membership.